

An Open-Cavity RCS Enhancement Device for Airborne Applications

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1 Abstract

We propose an open cavity embedded in the surface of an air vehicle as a way to increase its radar cross section (RCS). The scattering from such an open cavity embedded in an infinite ground plane is calculated using a boundary integral method. The boundary integral equations are solved numerically using the Method of Moments. Numerical results are compared with measurements for a cylindrically shaped open cavity.

2 Open-Cavity RCS Enhancement Device (OCRED)

Methods of radar cross section (RCS) reduction have been extensively investigated over the past several decades and have reached a state of maturity sufficient to find many practical applications. On the other hand, methods of RCS enhancement have received only limited attention. RCS enhancement of airborne vehicles has a number of important applications, including increasing the ability to track remotely-piloted vehicles (RPVs) with radar, using small unmanned air vehicles (UAVs) as tactical decoys for physically larger aircraft, and controlling an air vehicle's radar signature to aid in non-cooperative identification. Several techniques have been considered to accomplish effective RCS enhancement, including impedance loading [2] and various broadband reflectors, such as trihedrals, bicones, or dielectric lenses [3]. These methods have several disadvantages, including decreased aerodynamic performance through increased drag, and additional parasitic weight. A potentially viable candidate design for an RCS enhancement device consists of one or more open cavities embedded behind the air vehicle's exterior skin. Figure 1 shows a possible location of an open cavity on an unmanned air vehicle (UAV) - on the upper surface of its wing.

Figure 1: An open cavity embedded in the wing of a UAV

3 Integral Equations

We use a set of integral equations developed by Asvestas & Kleinman [1] to calculate the scattering from an arbitrarily shaped open cavity embedded in a perfectly conducting ground plane. The surface of the cavity is perfectly conducting, and the cavity interior is filled with free space. The governing integral equations are written as

$$jk\hat{z} \times \vec{H}(\vec{r}') - \hat{z} \times \int_S \hat{n} \times \vec{H}(\vec{r}) \cdot \vec{\Gamma}(\vec{r}, \vec{r}') ds = jk\hat{z} \times \vec{H}^{inc}(\vec{r}') \quad \text{for } \vec{r}' \in \sigma \quad (1)$$

$$2\hat{n}' \times \int_\sigma \hat{z} \times \vec{H}(\vec{r}) \cdot \vec{\Gamma}(\vec{r}, \vec{r}') d\sigma + \hat{n}' \times \int_S \hat{n} \times \vec{H}(\vec{r}) \cdot \vec{\Gamma}_2(\vec{r}, \vec{r}') ds = \frac{jk}{2} \hat{n}' \times \vec{H}(\vec{r}') \quad \text{for } \vec{r}' \in S \quad (2)$$

where S is the surface of the cavity, σ is the aperture between the open cavity and the half space above the ground plane, $\hat{n} \times$ is the outward-pointing unit normal vector on S , $\vec{H}$ is the magnetic field vector, k is the wavenumber, $\vec{H}^{inc}$ is the incident magnetic field, and $\vec{r}$ and $\vec{r}'$ are position vectors on S or σ . The integral dyadic kernel in equation (1) is given by $\vec{\Gamma}(\vec{r}, \vec{r}') = -jk\nabla G(\vec{r}, \vec{r}') \times \vec{\Gamma}$ with $G(\vec{r}, \vec{r}') = \exp(k|\vec{r} - \vec{r}'|)/(4\pi|\vec{r} - \vec{r}'|)$. The kernel in the second integral of equation (2) is a half-space form of $\vec{\Gamma}$, as defined in [1].

4 Moment Method Solution

Equations (1) and (2) can be numerically solved using the well-known method of moments [4]. We restrict the geometry to bodies of revolution (BORs), since their scattering characteristics are azimuth-independent, as desirable property for

and RCS enhancement device. We employ basis functions which are separable functions of rotation angle and arc length along the generating arc of the BOR, and use Galerkin testing.

5 Results

The moment method solution outlined in Section 4 provides the tangential magnetic field on the cavity surface S , which can then be used to find the far-zone scattered fields using the standard radiation integral [5].

Figure 2 shows the monostatic radar cross section of a cylindrical open cavity in an infinite ground plane. The cavity is 7.62 cm deep and its radius is 1.59 cm. The method of moments results are plotted in solid and dashed lines, while the measured RCS of a full-scale physical model is plotted using symbols. The calculated results are in excellent agreement with the measured values at all tested frequencies.

Figure 2: The RCS of a cylindrical OCRED as a function of angle from normal at four discrete frequencies (6.9, and 10 GHz).

The magnitude and phase of the tangential magnetic field on the aperture and surface of the cylindrical cavity is shown in Figure 3. Since the cavity is a BOR, the field can be decomposed into Fourier components; Figure 3 shows only the $m = 1$ Fourier component. The cylindrical cavity supports the TE_{11} cylindrical waveguide mode [5], and at a frequency of 6.9 GHz, the cavity is very nearly one modal wavelength deep. This is evidenced by the "double hump" pattern evident in Figure 3. Also evident is a sharp spike in the magnetic field parallel to the edge of the rim, as predicted by Meixner [6].

6 Conclusions

A method has been described to predict the radar cross section of an open cavity embedded in an infinite ground plane. This is used to model an open-cavity RCS

Figure 3: The tangential magnetic field plotted as a function of arc length ℓ for the cylindrical OCRED: $f = 6.9$ GHz, $\theta = 60^\circ$, and $m = 1$. The aperture rim corresponds to $\ell = 1.59$ cm.

enhancement device for use on airborne platforms. Numerical and experimental results agree very well.

References

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